

**Artistic interpretation of the national image of a person in the stories of
Shukur Kholmiraev**

Mamayusupova Saodat Mamatkulovna

Senior Lecturer, JDPU

Abstract

This article presents an opinion about the artistic interpretation of the national image of a person in the stories of Shukur Kholmiraev.

Key words: essay, badia, versatile, creative, contrary, national character, cruel, realism.

Sh. Kholmiraev entered literature with a wide range of life impressions. Mythical characters such as dragon, giant, fairy, Khizr have a wide place in popular fantasy. These images created in the human imagination are also used in written literature, they are widely used to express a certain ideological-artistic goal, to describe the character and image of a person. In some mythical images, people's dreams, sweet dreams, passions, and warm relationships are expressed, and their views on dragons, giants, demons, demons, and other evil forces are manifested. Mythical images reach their level of permanence, stability, vitality in folklore. But in each mythical image there is a leading character, and the first image of this image appears when we mention it. For example, the leading feature for a fairy is beauty, Khizr is a symbol of immortality, a giant is power and evil, a dragon is horror and cruelty, the owner of a nuisance.

The writer chooses simple, everyday events for his stories, combines myths and national values and reveals the reality based on simplicity. Koziboy in the story "The

Old Man" wakes up after seeing his grateful old woman in a dream, while he remembers his wife, the old man complains of the corns rustling outside and the dog barking, and he says to himself: "Hey, now is the time," he thought, laying on the bed, while sitting down. - The day is over now... My grateful old lady also felt it. The late wife is sucking the hand of the deceased saying, "Walk, walk!" The old man woke up and interpreted this dream in a bad way. [Election Volume 1, page 288]

Well, the dog doesn't bark in vain, does it? I've run out of food too... Sustenance is being cut off. Now we need to prepare." By giving a mythopoetic image of a dream, the writer seems to make the old man Koziboy feel that his death is near. Is it really so? When he goes to bed after seeing the dream, the next day when his neighbor Jamalboy comes to the herd of the goats, he sees him and brings out a bowl of bitter soup from his house, and he is refreshed after drinking the soup.

"Bahai, what's going on in the world?" he asked. - I... could not go to the market, Jamalboy! I was lying down feeling sick... I couldn't tell if the wind touched me. So?

- The news is that the district is full of people, said the neighbor. - They have returned from cotton, and your market is also crowded... Go outside, it will be fine.

- You are right. There is no use of sleeping! Koziboy couldn't go out until noon because of this. In the evening, for the first time in his life, he was supported by a cane. When he got to the center of the district, his mood became hot... E! The old man is really not alone! Even if he does not have a son, there are young people who respect him like his son... And old people of his age also show him respect. Here, the writer very beautifully expresses the fact that his friends of Korean and Tajik nationality asked him how he was doing. Why did he add people of other nationalities? What is the purpose and intention of the writer? We seem to have found an answer to this in the course of events. These Korean comrades do not forget their old customers; They were also forbidden to sell rice so that the people who were going to cotton would

not be distracted, so they took out their goods again. Everyone is happy! Old Koziboy inquired with them and entered the tea house.

When he went out, he ran into Tajik cooks who had come down from the mountain to buy soap and salt. They asked the old man how he was doing very eloquently.

- There are plenty of pits now! - they said. - Thank you... Don't forget us, you won't be hurt. After one hundred and sixty-five days, the hole came out!

"Yes, let him be patient with death, everything will be fine," said the old man.

On his way home, he passed by the butcher's shop, and his tongue hurt. Now he remembered that his friend had not received a message... [selection volume 1 page 289]

He had given a thousand soums to his butcher friend and bequeathed it to be used for him if he dies. The butcher used up the old man's money right away, because he knew that this man had no one, that he was a God-fearing person and that he would walk away from fights and quarrels. He said:

- Yes, I will make a will as soon as I remember, my friend. I have not eaten for a week! You're busy with work... So you don't even know I'm dead, ok? Therefore, if you send your table every three days and ask how I am doing, give me one soum of that money...

Why does the writer encourage the old man Koziboy to give the bequest money to the butcher Kobil. There were neighbors around. In my opinion, old Koziboy knew that there is always money in the butcher. Old man Koziboy also knew that one kilo of meat is very expensive among all foods and that meat cannot be sold without bones. That is why he gave the money to the butcher. It was Kobil who gave to the butcher, because he who saw the market knew that everything was for sale and who had the money permanently. It is also possible that the writer, based on his own life experience, wrote the incident of giving money to Kobil the butcher, bringing to mind

the swearing butchers who took their goods and sold their meat without giving the money to many people. As a result, Kobil the butcher betrays the deposit. Old Koziboy, with tears streaming down his eyes, cries in a faint voice. Until recently, the entire seven neighborhoods heard his voice during the beginning of the work.

The profession of the old man Koziboy is bad. It is sold on market days. In particular, he prays to those who have lost their property: "He is a calf, one leg is black, two years old! Whoever caught, saw, or tied, thirty sums of water, when he started shouting, his voice would go seven neighborhoods [selection volume 1, p. 283]

After hearing about the betrayal of his deposit, he cries, because his voice becomes weak and he can't cry when he hears that his honest money was betrayed.

- Don't say I didn't hear! He has a prize... Kobil the butcher is a low man. I had given a thousand soums for my death, he didn't admit it! People! That money was your money. You paid for my honest work. I gave it to this person and told him to use this for my death ...He didn't admit it. He's going to rob now... People, Kobil the butcher is a scoundrel! He eats away the rights of a person... I wish from God that his dead body remains on the street, people... He left me without cerement, people! [Election Volume 1, page 292]

On the one hand, the old man Koziboy, who earned a decent living, put the butcher to shame. The crowd in the market knew, at least partially, what kind of butcher he was. The people of the bazaar protected him because they knew the old man Koziboy well. Old Koziboy made a wish to God and cursed him very hard. On the other hand, after this incident, the old man will be refreshed and become the same again.

"How can I die in this situation?" It's impossible, at all... I have to work again. I need to earn honest money. I have to die... If I die after that, it's another matter..."

He was forcing the food that the neighbor brought out. He got up in the middle of the night and roasted meat. Sahar woke up in the morning and went down to the river.

Washed. Refreshed, he went to the street... Old Koziboy became the same as before.

[Selection Volume 1, page 292]

The end of thoughts and desires in the depths of old man Koziboy's mental world goes back to folk traditions. The work depicts such images very convincingly.

In this story of Shukur Kholmirzaev, we can say that the issue of bringing a person back to life is fully reflected in the work. Old man Koziboy is a hero who was able to preserve his dignity and humanity. The characters of the second story, Samar and Hidayat, are told the events that created the perfect Uzbek character. The characters of Samar and Hidayat are alive, the growth in the psyche of the characters is the reason why we can say that the writer was able to see life with an impartial eye and describe it sincerely as he sees it. We can say without a doubt that the main subject of literary literature is man, and all his complexities, good and bad have achieved true illumination in the work of art. I can say without hesitation that Shukur Kholmirzaev was able to artistically discover the main problem of these two stories, that is, the complex species called man, and even when he discovered it, he was able to reveal its hidden, hidden aspects, and through this, he was able to give eternal life to his stories.

The characters of Shukur Kholmirzaev's stories act like living people, and I think that we should teach them as a means of education in families, schools, and universities that their words and behavior are extremely natural. I can say that these two stories can be a source of guidance for education. We must not forget that Hidayat's coming from the village to the current education, running away to the city to study, walking to the city with torn legs, walking on dusty, dirt streets in the moonlight, helped us to recognize that he taught himself to help draw the necessary conclusion by comparing the current and previous life. I think that it is necessary to

discuss the opinions about what happened to Samar Hidayat, because the story ended as it should.

Our people's national image, character, unique way of life, heart, humanity, dreams, aspirations, virtues and shortcomings, in a word, the whole existence of our various national values, i.e. in weddings, family celebrations, parades and ceremonies, funerals it is evident in the events dedicated to their memories.

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